

Coping in the face of Economic Recession: An Analysis of Undergraduate Students' Experiences in Niger Delta University, Amassoma

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Abstract

This study investigated the coping strategies of undergraduate students in Nigeria during the period of economic recession, using the Niger Delta University (NDU), Amassoma, Bayelsa State as a case study. It consisted of a population of 202 students who were sampled using the multi-stage sampling technique. The work adopted the psychological stress/coping and student engagement theories as its theoretical mooring. Data were primarily collected using a structured questionnaire and using statistics such as frequencies, percentages and mean and inferential statistics such as binary logistics regression and Pearson correlation through the aid of the SPSS. Findings from the study showed that the recent economic recession has brought severe hardship on a majority of undergraduates at NDU. It also revealed the various coping strategies of the students, including engaging in part-time jobs and Ponzi Schemes, resorting to buying food on credit, and playing leech on others that may be well off, based on these findings, the study recommended that the university authority should encourage entrepreneurial activities on campus which will encourage students to engage in productively creative economic activities in order to raise fund for themselves.

Keywords: Economic recession, Coping strategies, Economic hardship, GDP, Academic performance

Introduction

The Nigerian economy was formally declared to have entered recession in 2016 having recorded as low as 0.36% -1.5% and 0.8% growth rates in the first, second and fourth quarters in 2016 respectively (Noko, 2017). In the same year, Nigeria was ranked 169th out of 190 countries in ease of doing business in the world (World Bank Doing Business, 2017). Among the sub-Saharan African countries, Nigeria was ranked 36th out of 47 countries in the same year in ease of doing business, while Mauritius, Rwanda and South Africa were placed first, second and third positions respectively (Udo, 2016). There is no agreement among scholars or authorities on factors that were actually responsible for the recession. For instance, the World Bank attributed it to lack of enforcement of contracts. In its 2016 report (cited in Akpan, 2017), Nigeria ranked 23rd in enforcing contracts and 28th in managing insolvency in the region. Another report of the Resource Governance Index (cited in Akpan, 2017), found out that Nigeria scored 66% and 18% respectively in institutional and legal setting and enabling environment out of 58 countries surveyed.

Noko (2017) on his own part, identified the following factors as responsible for Nigeria's economic recession: high inflation rate, accumulation of debt servicing, high interest rate, fall in aggregate demand, wages and income, mass unemployment, poor economic planning, high tax, and policy conflict. Recession has been described as a broad-based decline in gross domestic product (GDP) that lasts for months (Uchem, 2009). Using the decline in the GDP as an indicator of economic recession, Bassey (2016) argues that the Nigerian economy has plunged deeper into recession as GDP contracted 2.24 per cent (year-on-year) in real terms in the third quarter of 2016, from 2.06 per cent from the previous quarter. Real GDP for the third quarter stood at about N1.78 trillion, the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) said in its GDP report (2017). As such, the contraction of the economy in the third quarter was lower by 0.18 per cent points from the preceding quarter, according to the report. The report further reveals a figure that was also lower by 5.08 per cent points from the growth recorded in the corresponding quarter of 2015. Details of the report show that aggregate GDP, in nominal terms at basic prices, stood at N26.6 trillion, against the N24.3 trillion in the third quarter of 2015. "During the quarter, aggregate GDP stood at N26.6 trillion (in nominal terms) at basic prices, compared to the third quarter 2015 value of N24.3 trillion. Nominal GDP grew by 9.23 per cent. This growth was higher relative to growth recorded in the third quarter of 2015 by 3.22 per cent points" (Bassey, 2006).

Accordingly, the NBS (2017) claims that, the recession marked Nigeria's worst economic period in 29 years, with 2016 seeing Nigeria's economy shrink by 1.51 percent overall. These reports are in line with the of Okonjo-Iweala that, "Nigeria will be hit by the global economic crisis together with developed and developing countries all over the world" (Okonjo-Iweala, 2009). The impact of the crisis was felt differently by all Nigerian citizens. For a state such as Bayelsa the impact of the recession was a bitter episode owing to a number of factors peculiar to its economic terrain because a majority of its workers are civil servants. In a report published by THISDAY in July 6, 2016, was reported that Bayelsa, like many other states in Nigeria, is going through perhaps its worst economic crisis in recent years, owing to the drastic reduction in its revenue arising from the drop-in oil prices (2016) Like in many other southern states in Nigeria, the economy of Bayelsa

Sate received some serious bashing as a result of the slump in crude oil prices and by extension, the allocation accruing to the state from the federal government. In effect, workers of all cadres, including political appointees were owed salaries. Correspondingly, the economic recession placed a huge strain on the country and the citizen to react differently, Undergraduates were not exempted as they were fraught with huge challenge coping with the recession. The economic crisis resulted in too many lamentations especially among the youths who were in higher institutions. Youderwei, Uwandu, and Iruoma, (2016) state that students in Lagos were bitter over the recession as it impacted negatively on their normal way of survival Youdeowei et al. (2016) succinctly capture the wailing of 200-levels student of the University of Lagos thus,

I barely survive as my parents had to slash my allowance from 420,000 to N15, 000. Her words, "That N5, 000 removed seems little but it feels as if half of the money was removed. How do I feed, pay for my assignments at the print stand, eat and afford other miscellaneous expenses like toiletries and even recharging my phones? "What our parents and government don't know is that if they are forcing us to cut comers, some students might attempt to go into armed robbery, for the guys or engage in prostitution as a female. Government should find ways to increase workers' salary, our parent's wages, else they will see an increase of youth's misdemeanor.

In an effort to cope during the period of the recession, students devised survival mechanisms as prices of foodstuff such as *garri* (cassava flour). rice, beans, bread, among others soared by over 100 per cent. A bag of rice previously sold between N11,000 to N14,000 was sold at between N22,000 to N24,000. A bowl of *garri* formerly at N300 was sold at N500; a bread of N250 later became N400, etc. Many families resorted to cheap and affordable food substitutes such as cocoyam and in Yenagoa, for instance, families started consuming locally made bread popularly known as Madiga, even though it is said to high in bromate-a cancer-causing chemical additive. Many parents withdrew their children from private schools since they could no longer afford the high tuition fees (Vanguard, Oct 10, 2016). Most studies done after the recession focused on the economic, health and demographic implications. Though this study also falls under one of these categories, however, it isolated the students' community and explored how that segment of the society coped during the period of the recession.

Theoretical Framework

The psychological stress/coping and student engagement theories served as the theoretical bases for this study. The psychological stress/coping theory was advanced by a number of psychological theorists to explain how economic crises result to stress among people and how people eventually cope during financial crises. Some of the proponents of this theory include: Seyle (1974); Smith (1987); and Folkman and Lazarus (1980). The theory is grounded on the principle that the interaction between a stressor, an external condition and the condition of an individual produces stress (Smith, 1987). This theory further advanced that individuals react to stress by coping, which is the cognitive and behavioural efforts made to master, tolerate, or reduce external and internal demands and conflict among them (Folkman & Lazarus, 1980). Strategies adopted in coping during financial crises according to this theory vary between and within individuals. Hence, stress

does not have a direct causal relationship with the coping strategy used by an individual (Folkman & Lazarus, 1980). The theory posits that coping styles could be divided into two broad categories, namely, problem-focused and emotional focused coping styles. In the problem-focused coping, individuals try to change the relationship with the stressor by engaging in an activity, e.g., working. The emotional-focused coping on the other hand, attempts to reduce the emotional responses produced by stress and maybe the only possible coping strategy for stressors out of their control (Folkman & Lazarus, 1980).

Viewing economic recession from this perspective and how students might cope with it, this theory explains that students react to a feeling that they unable to meet their needs as a result of recession. Hence, they might cope with their financial crisis through problem-focused strategy by working extra hours or borrowing more (Fasnacht, 2013), or emotional- 233 focused strategy by ignoring or distracting themselves from the problem, on more positive aspects of life, or exercising self-control. According to the students' engagement theory developed by Astin (1984), it posits that students' learning and development result from the time and quality of effort they put into educationally beneficial activities. Hence, financial crisis poses multiple barriers to the engagement of students' in spending time and quality of efforts in educationally beneficial activities (Fasnacht, 2013). In essence, if a student copes with financial stress by working more, he/she will devote less time to educationally beneficial activities, Similarly, if students worry over their financial conditions, they could be distracted from engaging meaningfully in their academics.

Materials and Methods

This study was carried out in the Niger Delta University, Amassoma, Bayelsa State. It sampled 202 undergraduate students registered at the 2016/2017 academic session. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design. The choice of this design was informed by its capacity to generate data quantitatively as well as providing the opportunity to carry out a study with a representative of the target population in order that generalizability can still be achieved of the entire population of study at a minimal cost.

In selecting the sample for the study, the researchers made use of multi-stage sampling technique, consisting of both the probable and non- probable sampling techniques. First, the study adopted the purposive sampling techniques to select undergraduate students of the Niger Delta University located at Amassoma community. The rationale for doing so is based on the main goal of the research. Second, the study also adopted the stratified random sampling techniques to categorize the target population into different faculties, after which the systematic sampling technique was used to select a total of six (6) faculties. This was done by assigning number to all twelve faculties and selecting the faculties with even numbers. Third, the random sampling was used to select twelve (12) departments (two from each faculty). Also, it is important to note that the ballot system was used to randomly select the number of departments to be surveyed.

Lastly, the accidental sampling technique was used to locate respondents in all the selected faculties and departments. This was done due to the absence of a well-structured sampling frame. Primary data for this study was collected with the use of a well-structured questionnaire. The

questionnaire had multiple close-ended questions format. In constructing the questionnaire, two major types of questions were asked in order achieve the goals of the study. These are:

1. Objective or general characteristics of the respondents, socio- to economic and demographic characteristics; and
2. Subjective questions that have to do with the opinions and attitudes of respondents to the problem under study, that is, the economic recession and student' coping strategies.

The questionnaire was divided into six major sections, The first section (Section A) was on the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents, while the remaining five sections dwelt on issues relating to the objective of the study. In analysing the data collected from the field, the researchers adopted the use of descriptive and inferential statistics since it was basically a quantitative study. As such, data that were nominal in nature were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies - used in analysing the socio- demographic characteristics of the respondents since these data are nominal and qualitative in nature. On the other hand, the data that are ordinal and quantitative in nature were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. For the descriptive statistics, mean and standard deviation were used, while for the inferential statistics, Pearson correlation and logistic regression was used through the aid of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS).

Results and Findings

It should be noted that out of the two hundred and two (202) copies of questionnaire distributed, only one hundred and ninety-seven (197) representing 97.5% were retrieved and found valid for analysis. Therefore, analysis of data collected from the field was based on the 197 copies that were found usable.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Profile of Respondents

S/N	Variables	Responses	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
1.	Faculty	Arts	40	20.3
		Engineering Pharmacy	40	20.3
		Social Sciences	40	20.3
		Sciences	38	19.3
		Law	39	19.8
			17	8.6
		Total = 197	100.0	
2.	Department	History and Diplomacy	17	8.6
		Fine/Industrial/Theatre Arts	17	8.6
			17	8.6

		Electronic/Electrical Engineering	17	8.6
		Civil Engineering	17	8.6
		Economics	17	8.6
		Political Science	17	8.6
		Biological Sciences	16	8.1
		Pure and Applied Chemistry	16	8.1
		Clinical/Pharmacy Practice	15	7.6
		Pharmaceutical Chemistry	14	7.1
		Jurisprudence/Public law	Total = 197	100.0
		Private/Property Law		
	Level of Study	100 levels	40	20.3
		200 levels	61	31.0
		300 levels	42	21.3
		400 levels	32	16.2
		500 levels	22	11.2
			Total = 197	100.0
3.	Hostel/Accommodation Location	Main Campus	40	20.3
		New-site	28	14.2
		Yenagoa Campus	20	10.2
		CHS Campus	18	9.1
		Off-Campus	91	46.2
			Total = 197	100.0
	Gender	Male	97	49.2
		Female	100	50.8
			Total = 197	100.0
	Age	<20	76	38.6
		20-29	103	52.3
		30 and Above	18	9.1
			Total = 197	100.0
	Parents' Economic Status	Very Rich	11	5.6
		Rich	60	30.5
			112	56.9
			14	7.1
			-	00
			Total 200	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2017

Table 1 classified the socio-demographic profile of the respondents into eight (8) categories. First, it classified the respondents in terms of their various faculties. It showed that

Faculties of Arts, Engineering and Pharmacy had a respondents' ratio of 20.3% each. The table also indicated that 19.3% of the respondents were from the Faculty of Social Sciences, while 19.8% of the respondents were from the Faculty of Law. In terms of department of the respondents, the study showed that 8.6% each e following departments, History and I from the follow of the respondents, Diplomacy, Fine/Industrial/ Theatre Arts, Electrical/Electronic Engineering. Civil Engineering Theatrics, Political Science, Biological Science, Pure/Applied Chemist 8.1% each of the respondents was froe the Departments of Clinical Also, aty practice, and Pharmaceutical Chance Public 2.6% of each of 8.1 them was from the Department of Jurisprudence/Public law, while 7.1% was from Private/Property Law.

In categorizing the respondents in terms of their levels of study, the study revealed that 20.3% of the respondents were in 100 levels; 31.0% were in 200 levels; 21.3% were in 300 levels; 16.2% were in 400 levels, 11.2% were in 500 levels. categorizing the respondents in terms of their sexes, it showed that 49.2% of the respondents were male, while 50.8% of the respondents were female. With regard to the ages of the respondents, the study indicated that 38.6% of the respondents were less than twenty years, 52.3% of the respondents were between the age bracket of 20-29; 9.1%, while 9.1.0% of the respondent were above 30 years of age. Lastly, as regards the economic status of parents of the respondents, it was found that 5.6% of their parents were very rich, 30.5% of them said their parents were rich, 56.9% of indicated that their parents were averagely rich, while only 7.1% of students indicated that their parents were poor.

Table 2: Economic State Undergraduate Students before Recession

Items/Questions	Responses	Frequencies	%
Do you get monthly income/ allowances before the recession?	Yes	175	88.8
	No	22	11.2
	Total = 197	100	
How much income/allowances do you receive monthly before the recession?	N3,000-N5,000	16	8.1
	N6,000-N9,000	21	10.7
	N10,000-N12,000	40	20.3
	13,000 and above	120	60.9
	Total = 197	100	
How many square meals do you always have before the recession?	One	-	-
	Two	89	45.2
	Three	108	54.8
	Total = 197	100	

Source: Field Survey: 2017

This analysis showed the economic state of undergraduate students before the recession. The first indicator was based on the monthly income/ allowance of the respondents before the recession. Hence, the study revealed in table 2 above that 88.8% the respondents received monthly

allowances before the recession, while 11.2% of the respondents were not receiving monthly allowances. The second indicator was based on the average monthly allowance before the recession. This revealed that 8.1% of the respondents received an average sum of between N3000-45000 only; 10,7% between N6000-N9000 only. 20.3% of the respondents received an average monthly allowance of between 10000- N120000 before recession, while 60.9% of the respondents received an average allowance of between 13000 and above.

Table 3: Experiences of Students in the Period of Recession

Items/Questions	Responses	Frequencies	(%)
Do you still get the exact monthly income/ allowances as at when due in this recession?	Yes	83	37.6
	No	114	62.4
		Total = 197	100
Have you ever attended class on empty stomach on more than two occasions in this recession?	Yes	76	38.6
	No	121	61.4
In this recession, do you have challenges buying all course materials?	Yes	144	73.1
	No	53	26.9
		Total = 197	100
Have you ever skipped class because of lack of transport fare?	Yes	74	37.6
	No	123	62.4
		Total = 197	100

Source: Field Survey, 2017

Table 3 above presents an analysis of the experiences of students during the period of recession. First, the study revealed that 37.6% of the respondents indicated that they were still receiving their monthly allowances, while 62.4% of the respondents stated that they stopped receiving their monthly allowances as a result of the economic recession.

Table 4: Factors Responsible for Economic Hardship in Recession

Items	Variable	Frequencies	Mean	Standard Deviation	Research Decision
Cat-down in monthly allowances makes living very difficult for students in this recession.	Strongly Agree	30	4.1	2.02	Accepted
	Agree	157			
	Neutral	-			
	Disagree	-			
	Strongly Disagree	Total = 197			

Inflation in the prices of goods and within the school services community is responsible for hardship among students	Strongly Agree Agree Neutral Disagree Strongly Disagree Total = 197	56 122 13 6 - Total = 197	4.14	2.03	Accepted
Expensive fare for shuttle buses and other transport means within and outside campus poses hardship on students	Strongly Agree Agree Neutral Disagree Strongly Disagree Total = 197	74 84 11 19 9 Total = 197	4	2	Accepted
Increment on school fees causes hardship among students.	Strongly Agree Agree Neutral Disagree Strongly Disagree Total = 197	95 80 3 18 1 Total = 197			Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2017

In table 4 above, it was found that all the array of factors listed in the table (cut in allowances, inflation, and increment in transport fares) obtained mean scores which was above 2.5, indicating by implication, that they are all linked to the economic hardship experienced by students during the recession.

Effects of Economic Recession on Undergraduate Students

Table 5: Social Implication of Economic Recession among Undergraduate Students

Items/Questions	Responses	Frequencies	(%)
In this recession do you share your meal with friends?	Yes	78	39.6
	No	119	60.4
	Total = 197		100
Do you get financial assistance from friends when you're stranded?	Yes	76	38.6
	No	121	61.4
	Total = 197		100

Are you able to engage in extra curriculum/ social activities within and outside campus?	Yes	96	73.1
	No	101	26.9
		Total = 197	100

Source: Field Survey, 2017

From table 5 above, the study revealed 39.6% of the respondents shared their meals with friends during the recession, while 60.4% of the indicated that they stopped sharing their meal with their friends due to the recession. In ascertaining if the respondents' got any financial assistance from friends when they are stranded, 38.6% of the respondents stated that they got financial assistance from friends when they were stranded, while 61.4% of them indicated that they did not get financial assistance from friends when stranded during the recession. Based on the effect of the recession on participating in extra curriculum/social activities on campus, the study discovered that 73.1% of the respondents indicated that they do not partake in any social activities due to the economic hardship experienced during the recession, 26.9% of them stated that they fully participated in social activities in spite of the recession.

Table 6: Academic Implication of Economic Recession among Undergraduate Students

Items/Questions	Responses	Frequencies	(%)
Current attendance rate	Above 70%	153	77.7
	Less than 70%	44	22.3
		Total = 197	100
Capacity to comprehend during personal study and in class	Above average	59	29.9
	Average	109	55.3
	Don't know	26	13.2
	Below average	3	1.5
		Total = 197	100
Performance in last semesters' continuous assessment	Very good	25	12.7
	Good	143	72.6
	Poor	29	14.7
	Very poor		
		Total = 197	100
Current C.G.P. A	1.00-1.9	9	4.6
	2.00-2.9	50	25.4
	3.00-3.9	130	66.0
	4.00-4.9	8	4.1
	5.00	-	-
		Total = 197	100

Source: Field Survey, 2017

The impact of economic recession on the academic performance of undergraduate student in Niger Delta University as shown in table 6 below revealed that 77.7% of the respondents had maintained above 70% attendance while 22.3% of them could not maintain 70% attendance. The research further showed the capacity of undergraduate students to comprehend during lectures on self-evaluation of the respondents. In this regard, 59 (29.9%) of the respondents affirmed that their capacity to comprehend was above average; 109 (55.3%) of them indicated that they were average students. 26 (13.2%) of the population could not rate their capacity to comprehend, while 3 (1.5%) stated that their capacity for comprehension was below average. Importantly, the last test was used to measure the academic performance of the respondents which revealed that the performance of 12.7% of the respondents scored themselves "very good"; 72.6% said that they were "good"; while 14.7% of them said they capacity was "poor" based on their last test performance. Also, in ascertaining the students current cumulative grade point average (CGPA), it was found that most respondents (66%) were having a CGPA of between 3.00 -3.90, this is followed by those with a CGPA of 2.00-2.90 (25.4%). Those with 4.00 and above where just 4.1%, while the smallest group consisted of those with a low CGPA of 1.00-1.90.

Analysis of the Coping Strategies of Undergraduate Students in Economic Recession

Table 7: Coping Strategies of Undergraduate Students in Economic Recession

Items/Questions	Responses	Frequencies	Percentage
Raising fund for payment of school fees during recession	Complete dependence on parents/sponsors	34	17.3
	Engage in small scale Business	53	26.9
	Engage Part-time job	52	26.4
	Engage Part-time job	34	17.3
	Online Ponzi scheme	24	12.2
	Appeal to a friend/close relative	Total = 197	100
Coping with the challenge of buying relevant course materials	Look for substitute in library	44	22.3
	Photocopy materials	102	51.8
	Borrow money to buy materials	19	14.2
	Borrow course material	4	9.6
	Others	Total = 197	2.0
Coping with the challenges of feeding in campus.	Buy food on credit	5	2.5
	Skip meals	59	29.9
	Visit a friend who has food	98	49.7
	Travel home to get food stuffs	32	16.2
	Others	3	1.3
	Total = 197	100	

Coping with the challenge of Transportation.	Trekking	61	31.0
	Skip classes	89	41.1
	Borrow money from a friend	52	26.4
	Others	7	3.5
	Total = 197	100	

Source: Field Survey, 2017

From the analysis of the coping strategies adopted by respondents in the period of the recession, the following results were obtained (see table 7 below). With regards to payment of school fees 17% of the respondents indicated that they completely depended on their parents/sponsors for the payment of their fees, 26.9% of them stated that they engaged in small businesses to pay their fees, 26.4% of the respondents in the study them pointed out that they engage in part-time jobs while schooling to pay their fees, 17.3% of the respondents revealed that they took to Online-Ponzi scheme (e.g. MMM) to raise money for their fees, while 12.2% of the respondents stated that attempt raising their school fees by appealing to friends and close relatives.

With respects to coping with the challenges of getting course materials for students reading during the recession, 22.3% of the respondents stated that they make use of the available course materials that is in the school library, Majority of the respondents (51.8%) indicated that they photocopy relevant pages in recommended text, 14.2% opined the they resort to borrowing materials from friends and course mates, while 2.0% of them out that they make use of other strategy to get materials (e.g. reading class notes, reading online materials etc.) With regards to coping with feeding during the recession, the result showed that 2.5% of the students revealed that they depend on buying food on credit, 29.95% stated that constantly skip meals, the highest number of the students(49.7%) indicated that they visit friends who have food to assist them with feeding, 9.6% of the students opined that they travel back home till their sponsors makes provision for them, while 2.0% of the respondents stated that they cope with the challenge of feeding through other means (e.g. buying of very cheap food stuffs, engaging in small scale farming etc). Lastly, the analysis of how students cope with transportation to classes revealed that; most of them (49%) skip classes as means of coping with transport fare to classes. In pressing further, on how they do this, the students stated that they only go to classes that lecturers take attendance seriously and the ones they perceive that they do This followed by those who revealed that the walk to their classes irrespective of the distance (31.0%). 26.4% pointed out that they borrow money from friends to pay for their transport fares to classes, while 3.5% of the students indicated that adopt other methods like waiting to get free cabs, using bicycles, relying on others to pay their fares.

Hypotheses Testing

In this section, the stated hypotheses were tested using the instruments of data analysis such as the Pearson product moment correlation coefficient and binary logistic regression at 0.05 significance level. In essence, values that are less than 0.05 are accepted as statically significant.

Null Hypothesis 1 (Ho₁): The socio-demographic characteristics of undergraduate students do not determine the type of hardship they experienced during the period of economic recession.

Table 8: Table 8: Binary Logistic Regression showing Variables in the Equation

	B	S.E.	Wald	Df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Sex	.311	.308	1.016	1	.314	1.365
Age	.622	.247	6.315	1	.012	1.862
Level	.064	.120	.281	1	.046	1.066
Step 1 ^a Department	-.146	.047	9.532	1	.002	.864
Parents	.570	.233	5.976	1	.015	1.768
Economic Status						
Constant	-2.078	1.028	4.082	1	.043	.125

a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: Sex, Age, Level, Department, and Parents' Economic Status.

In testing Ho₁, the binary logistic regression analysis shows that the demographic characteristics of respondents had the following probability values and interpretations (Sex-0.31 not significant; Age-0.01 significant; Department- 0.00 significant, Parental economic status-0.02). Based on the forgoing analysis, it is clear that all the values obtained from the logistic regression except sex could adequately explain a significant relation between demographic characteristics of the respondents and the type of hardship they experienced during the period of recession. The study, therefore, fails to uphold the null hypothesis for the said variables.

Null Hypothesis 2 (Ho₂): There is no significant relationship between parental economic status and the coping strategies of students.

Table 9: Correlation between Parental Economic status and Coping Strategies

	Respondents' Parents' Economic Status	Raising fund for school fees payment
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Respondents' Parents' Economic Status	Pearson Correlation	1	.015
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.837
	N	197	197
Raising fund for school fees payment	Pearson Correlation	.015	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.837	
	N	197	197

In testing if the economic status of undergraduate students correlates with the coping strategies, the table above revealed the results of the Pearson Correlation of 0.015, while the p-value is 0.837. hence, the study fails to reject the null hypothesis of no significant difference between parental economic status and coping strategies.

Null Hypothesis 3 (Ho,): Cut-down of monthly allowance have no relationship with academic performance.

Table 10: Correlations between cut in monthly allowance and academic performance

		Reduction in Monthly Allowance.	Current CGPA
Reduction in Monthly Allowance.	Pearson Correlation	1	-.209**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003
	N	197	197
Current CGPA	Pearson Correlation	-.209**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	
	N	197	197

The third hypothesis which sought to test relationship between cut down of students' monthly allowance and academic performance revealed a Person correlation of 0.209 and a p-value of 0.003, indicating a statistical significance level between the two variables. Hence, the study fails to affirm the hypothesis of no significant relationship between the two variables.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study concluded that economic recession placed severe hardship on undergraduate students thus making academic life insufferable as there was massive inflation in the prices of goods and services within the NDU environment and the society at large. The recession cuts across all socio-economic statuses of parents and students. However, students adopted coping strategies, including skipping meals to relying on friends for help; engaging in part-time businesses; walking long distances; and engaging in Ponzi-schemes. In view of this, parents, students and the government at different levels should be encouraged to engage in the practice of saving for rainy days' to help curb the impact of consequent recession which might not be in a national scale but either at the state or family levels. The conclusion reached is that the

recession had an impact on the academic performance of students. Based on this, the following recommendations are proffered: the government should take adequate steps to subsidize tertiary education for parental/guardian financial sustainability, relevant university authorities should be able to encourage entrepreneurial activities on campuses which will in turn spur students to engage in productive economic activities to raise lawful fund for themselves. Also, universities in collaboration with other private organisations could create the working and schooling programme on campuses where students have the opportunities of working in their free periods to help meet their financial obligations to the school authorities and society.

References

- Akpan, M.J.D. (2017). Economic recession in Nigeria: An assessment of legal resolution of contracts and insolvency disputes. *International Journal of Development and Economic* 5(5), 1-10.
- Astin, A.W. (1984), Student involvement: A developmental theory for higher education: *Journal of College Student Personnel*, 25 (4), 297-308.
- Bassey U, (2016). Nigeria: Economic recession deepens as GDP contracts 2.24 percent third quarter. *Premium Times*. Retrieved from [http:// allafrica.com/stories/201611220039.html](http://allafrica.com/stories/201611220039.html)
- Effrosyni A., & Guila, M. T. (2014). "Academic performance and the great recession. Retrieved from [https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/54913/ 1/MPRA paper 54913.pdf](https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/54913/1/MPRA_paper_54913.pdf) original version (application/pdf)
- Folkman, S., & Lazarus, R.S. (1980) An analysis of coping in a middle- aged community sample. *Journal of Health and Social Behaviour*, 21(3), 219-239.
- Fosnacht, K. (2013). Undergraduates coping with financial crises: A latent class analysis. A Paper presented at the annual meeting of the American College Personnel Association in Las Vegas, March 2013.
- Kuh, G.D., Schuh, J.H., Whitt, E.J., & Associates (1991). *Involving Colleges: Successful approaches to Fostering Student Learning and Development Outside the Class Room*, San Francisco: Jossey- Bass
- National Bureau of Statistics. (2017). *Nigerian Gross Domestic Product Report (Q4 2016)*. Retrieved from [http://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/ download/518](http://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/download/518).
- Noko, E. J. (2017). Economic recession in nigeria: causes and solutions. Retrieved from; educainfo.com/economicrecession.

Okonjo-Iweala N. (2009). The global financial crisis: impact and implications for Nigeria. A distinguished lecture delivered at the Borok

March 16, 2009. Published by the Economic Confidential Magazine, April, 2009, 2 Pace, C.R (1984). Measuring the quality of college student experiences: An account of the development and use of college student experiences questionnaire. Los Angeles: Higher education Research Institute.

Smith, W.K. (1987). The Stress analogy, *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, 13(2), 215-220

THISDAY (2016). Weathering Bayelsa's economic storm. Retrieved from: <http://www.pressreader.com/nigeria/thisday/20160706281857232860135>

Uchem R.O. (2010). The global economic crisis: implication in Nigeria *International Journal of Economic Development Research and Investment*, 1(1), 62-75.

Udo F. (2016). How can Nigeria get out of Recession? Retrieved from www.punchng.com.

Vanguard (2016). Recession: We are dying, Nigerians lament. Retrieved from <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2016/10/were-dying-nigerians-lament/>

World Bank. (2017). Doing business: Measuring business regulations Retrieved from <http://www.doingbusiness.org/data/explorceconomies/nigeria>.

Youdewei T., Uwandu E., & Iruoma I. (2012). Recession: Measures students take to survive. Retrieved from <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2016/11/recession-measures-students-take>.